

RECIPROCAL VALUE OF SMES PRODUCTS IN STRENGTHENING SUSTAINABLE GREEN COMPETITIVENESS FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This study aims to examine the variables of Green Consumerism, Green Brand Image, Green Competitive Position, and Sustainable Competitive Advantage. As well as investigating the Reciprocal of Value Product (RVP) in strengthening the competitive position of green products of Indonesian SMEs.

Theoretical Framework: This research is developed from theories of sustainable business models, green marketing, and competitive advantage. The novelty of 'Reciprocal of Value Product' (RVP) integrates company value creation with socio-environmental values, emphasizing sustainable reciprocity.

Method: Primary data were collected using interviews, surveys, and field studies of 315 SMEs producing environmentally friendly products in Indonesia using purposive non-random sampling techniques using Structural Equation Modeling analysis.

Results and Discussion: The findings reveal that Environmental Sustainability positively and significantly affects RVP. RVP has a significant positive impact on Green Consumerism and Green Competitive Position. Also, Green Consumerism shows a positive and significant influence on Green Brand Image. These relationships highlight the interconnected nature between sustainable business practices and market competitiveness.

Research Implications: This study shows that Indonesian SMEs can adopt RVP into their strategic framework. The research findings show that sustainable practices increase the perceived value of products, which in turn affects green consumer behaviour and competitive positioning.

Originality: The main contribution of this research is the RVP to integrate corporate and socio-environmental value creation. Novelty offers valuable insights for SMEs seeking to enhance their competitive advantage through sustainable practices in the global marketplace.

Keywords: environmental sustainability, green product, green packaging, green pricing, reciprocal value of product, SDGs 8, sustainable development goals (SDGs).

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1 INTRODUCTION

The development of sustainable business models that are environmentally friendly is an important issue for future business sustainability. The business world is required to adopt the concepts of green economy and circular economy in carrying out its business activities in order to create harmony between economic, social and environmental goals (Geissdoerfer *et al.*, 2017; Aqmala *et al.*, 2018)

SMEs in Indonesia play an important role in the national economy but have limitations in implementing green business models. As can be seen, exports of Indonesian food products are withdrawn and even denied circulation in destination countries for safety and quality reasons, ethylene oxide (EtO) pesticide residues, 2-chloro ethanol (2-CE) derivative compounds, foodborne disease problems, food board disease by several food safety authorities of export destination countries including Hong Kong (CFS), Singapore Food Agency (SFA) to Japan's Food Inspection Agency, the United States to European Union (EU) countries. (Nasution, 2022; ARIF *et al.*, 2023)

EU regulations and policies are encouraging product businesses to switch to green or sustainable products. They apply labelling and certification of green products that will enter their market to make it easier for consumers to identify green products. Brown *et al.*, (2020) The research findings state that EU citizens are health conscious and the vegetarian, vegan and organic trend is gaining momentum with education from a young age (Arenas-Jal *et al.*, 2020; Noguero *et al.*, 2021).

European society's concern for personal and family health is influenced by a complex range of social, cultural and policy factors including Cultural and Historical Factors, Health Systems, Education and Awareness, Social Factors and economic factors. (Klebl *et al.*, 2024; Firmansyah *et al.*, 2024)

The result of the rejection has implications for the Indonesian economy, which fell by 5.04% compared to 2022. According to Esubalew & Raghurama, (2020) This impact has a significant effect on some of the performance of SMEs in the food consumption sector. Likewise, the report on the development of the Indonesian and world economies in 2023 by the Ministry of National Development Planning/Bappenas also explained the decline in the performance of various economic sectors in Indonesia (Irawati, 2023).

Regarding the environment and sustainable agricultural products (Chavan & Alam, 2020), the Government of Indonesia has regulated through legal products, namely the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 32 of 2009 (UU No.23/2009) concerning Environmental Protection and Management. Law No. 3 of 2014 (UU No.3/2014) requests that the production process prioritise efforts to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the use of resources in a sustainable manner so as to be able to harmonise industrial development with the preservation of environmental functions and can provide benefits to the community, as mandated in the National Industrial Development Master Plan 2015-2035 emphasises the achievement of competitive and environmentally sound advantages. As well as Government Regulation (PP) Number 22 of 2021 concerning the Implementation of Environmental Protection and Management.

On the administrative side, many Indonesian exporters face difficulties in fulfilling complex documentation requirements. The traceability system demanded by the European market often cannot be fulfilled due to manual and non-standardised record-keeping at the farm level. This is compounded by a lack of understanding of the ever-changing and increasingly stringent EU regulations (Žuraulis & Pečeliūnas, 2023).

Chopra *et al.*, (2022) The issue of sustainability has also been highlighted. Agricultural practices in Indonesia are still often criticised for their environmental impacts, including excessive pesticide use and deforestation issues. The carbon footprint of Indonesian agricultural products tends to be high due to inefficient production and transport processes.

The government encourages SMEs to be able to market their organic products in the global market, while global businesses impose environmental sustainability business labelling. Thus, to penetrate the international market,

Indonesian SMEs must comply with these global business rules (Lumban *et al.*, 2019; Sudoyo, 2021; Rulinawaty *et al.*, 2024) It should be noted that the safety of these food products should also be done in the country before they are marketed abroad.

Previous research found that inter-firm R&D collaboration practices involving family firms play a positive role in creating green innovation value, which contributes to sustainable competitive advantage (Ardito *et al.*, 2019). The findings Awan *et al.*, (2021) that the Company needs to conduct knowledge acquisition for integrated environmental investment to enhance product innovation, as well as environmentally friendly processes, with the aim of sustainable competitive advantage.

In line with the research results, environmental management systems contribute positively to sustainability development, thereby increasing competitive advantage (Ikram *et al.*, 2019; Batu & Setiyaningrum, 2019;). However, the object of research with agricultural companies cannot explore the business environment situation so that its influence on Sustainable Competitive Advantage is weak (Xi *et al.*, 2022). Research Swalehe *et al.*, (2020) also mentioned that companies can reduce operating costs, and increase employee satisfaction and environmental improvements but the impact is weak on Sustainable Competitive Advantage (Suasih *et al.*, 2024).

This research resolves the research gap by developing environmentally friendly product production from the production process, utilisation to disposal. This is not an easy task due to limited capital and human resources in the context of sustainable development goals (SDGs) for economic growth. Meanwhile, the production cost of environmentally friendly products is quite high (Mandagie *et al.*, 2024).

Therefore, this study aims to find and test new concepts to bridge the research gap with the formulation of the problem whether Green Consumerism, Green Brand Image and whether Green Competitive position affect Sustainable Competitive advantage and how the role of Reciprocal of Value Product between Environmental Sustainability to Sustainable Competitive advantage strengthens the positional competitiveness of green products of Indonesian SMEs in the global market.

2 METHODOLOGY

This research uses positivism thinking with quantitative research and multivariate analysis. The type of data is primary data with data collection techniques through interviews, surveys, and field studies on MSMEs on 5 major islands in Indonesia, namely Java, Bali, Kalimantan, Sumatra and Sulawesi with the assumption that the five islands can represent a sample of Indonesian MSMEs. The object of this research is MSMEs that produce green products that have been exported following global green rules. The sample technique used was purposive non-random sampling with a sample size of 315 respondents. Following the sample adequacy requirements, the number of instruments is multiplied by 5 so that the sample is $45 \times 5 = 225$, meaning that the planned number of samples has met the processing requirements with the structural equation model (SEM) (Werner & Schermelleh-Engel, 2010; Hair Jr *et al.*, 2021;)

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 RESULTS

Qualitative analysis allows researchers to gain a deeper understanding of a phenomenon. The qualitative approach is used to explore new concepts without being limited by pre-existing hypotheses or frameworks. Some previous research is presented in the following table

Table 1

Findings of Previous Research

Researcher	Analysis	Findings
Schaltegger <i>et al.</i> , (2019)	Literature Review	Sustainability strategy and business decision-making process to create value
Drempetic <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	SEM-AMOS	Companies with superior sustainability performance achieve sustainable competitive advantage
Dhanda & Shrotryia, (2021)	Literature Review	The sustainability revolution achieving sustainability excellence and sustainable business model transformation
(Consolandi <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	Regresi panel	sustainable business model transformation. Equity performance impact, rewarding more industrial companies with high levels of ESG materiality concentration.
(Liboni <i>et al.</i> , 2023)	SEM-AMOS	Need behavioural and cultural change, dynamic capabilities. For corporate business strategy, sustainability

In the following discussion of table 1, The table shows the development of research related to sustainability in the context of business and corporate strategy. Some research findings lead to the idea of reciprocal value creation between companies and stakeholders through sustainability practices.

Drempetic *et al.*, (2020a) Used SEM-AMOS analysis to show that companies with superior sustainability performance can achieve sustainable competitive advantage. This finding implies a reciprocal relationship between sustainability practices and firm value, which is in line with the concept of Reciprocal of Value Product. Study Dhanda & Shrotryia, (2021) revealed the importance of the sustainability revolution in achieving competitive advantage and sustainable business model transformation. This suggests that companies need to adopt a holistic approach to sustainability, which could include the concept of Reciprocal of Value Product as part of their strategy.

Research Consolandi *et al.*, (2022) Using panel regression to analyse the impact of equity performance on firms with a high concentration of ESG materiality. This finding reinforces the idea that focusing on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) aspects can add value to the company, which is an important element in the Reciprocal of Value Product. Liboni *et al.*, (2023) emphasises the importance of behavioural change, culture and dynamic capabilities in integrating sustainability into a company's business strategy. This suggests that the implementation of concepts such as Reciprocal of Value

Product requires fundamental changes in the way companies operate and think about value creation.

The findings of this research are that the novelty of the Reciprocal of Value Product concept lies in its explicit integration between the creation of corporate value and socio-environmental value, and its emphasis on sustainable reciprocal relationships between companies and stakeholders. It can be defined as follows Company products that are reciprocally given additional value to provide mutual benefits to the agreed product. this variable is thought to increase performance.

This concept can be a valuable framework for companies to design sustainability strategies that are not only financially beneficial, but also have a significant positive impact on society and the environment. Although these studies do not directly address Reciprocal of Value Product, they provide a strong foundation for the development and application of the concept.

Figure 1
 Results of model processing with SEM AMOS

The results of AMOS SEM processing in Figure 1 can be explained as follows Chi-Square (χ^2) = 540.839 with Cut-off: p-value > 0.05 means that the P-value shown is 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05. This indicates that there is

a significant difference between the proposed model and the observed data. However, Chi-Square is very sensitive to large sample sizes, so we need to check other fit indices.

GFI (Goodness of Fit Index) = 0.871 with Cut-off: > 0.90 meaning that the GFI value is slightly below the recommended cut-off, indicating marginal model fit. AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index) = 0.845 with Cut-off: > 0.90 meaning AGFI is also below the cut-off, consistent with GFI, indicating a less than optimal model fit. CFI (Comparative Fit Index) = 0.932 with Cut-off: > 0.95 meaning the CFI indicates a good fit, although slightly below the ideal cut-off of 0.95. TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index) = 0.924 with Cut-off: > 0.95 meaning that the TLI indicates a fairly good fit, although still below the ideal cut-off.

RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation) = 0.052 with Cut-off: < 0.08 (better if < 0.05) meaning the RMSEA indicates a good fit, falling between 0.05 and 0.08. Cmin/DF (Normed Chi-Square) = 1.717 with Cut-off: < 3 (more conservative < 2) meaning that this value indicates a very good fit, below 2. Considering these statistical results, it can be concluded that this model is acceptable and analysis of the variables is carried out.

Green Product Design is an approach to creating environmentally friendly products. Based on the analysis of existing data, environmentally friendly product design (X2) is the strongest indicator with a factor loading of 0.85. This shows that design aspects that pay attention to environmental impacts are very important and have a major influence in the concept of Green Product Design.

Meanwhile, the X1 indicator has a factor loading of 0.61 and X3 with a factor loading of 0.57 also makes a significant contribution, although not as strong as X2. These two indicators still play an important role in shaping the overall Green Product Design construct. The existence of error terms (e1-e3) and Ze1 indicates that there are still other variables outside the model that can affect the results. This is reasonable in statistical analysis due to the complexity of the Green Product Design concept which cannot be explained by only three indicators.

Overall, the three indicators provide a good description of the Green Product Design construct, with particular emphasis on the importance of environmentally friendly product design as a major factor.

Green Packaging reflects a commitment to sustainable and environmentally friendly packaging. Based on data analysis, the X6 indicator shows the strongest influence with factor loading reaching 0.89. This indicates that the sustainable packaging aspect is a crucial element in the implementation of Green Packaging. The high loading value confirms that companies need to pay special attention to the development of sustainable packaging.

Meanwhile, indicators X5 and X4 each have a factor loading of 0.75, indicating an influence that is also quite strong in shaping the concept of Green Packaging. The equality of loading values on these two indicators indicates that both have the same level of importance in supporting the implementation of environmentally friendly packaging.

The existence of error terms (e4-e6) and Ze3 indicates that there are other factors outside the model that can affect the measurement results of Green Packaging. This indicates the complexity of the Green Packaging concept that cannot be fully explained by only these three indicators. Nevertheless, the three existing indicators have provided a comprehensive picture of the implementation of Green Packaging in the context of environmental sustainability.

Green Pricing reflects a pricing strategy that considers environmentally friendly aspects. Data analysis shows that indicator X9 has the strongest influence with a factor loading of 0.84. This confirms that pricing that considers environmental aspects is a very important factor in the implementation of Green Pricing. The high loading value indicates that companies need to pay special attention to pricing strategies that are aligned with the principles of environmental sustainability.

Indicator X7 with a factor loading of 0.73 and X8 with a factor loading of 0.69 also contribute significantly in forming the Green Pricing construct. Although the value is not as high as X9, these two indicators still show an important role in supporting environmentally friendly pricing strategies.

The existence of error terms (e7-e9) and Ze3 indicates that there are other factors outside the model that can affect the measurement results of Green Pricing. This shows that the concept of Green Pricing has a complexity

that cannot be fully explained by only these three indicators. Nevertheless, the three indicators have provided a good understanding of the implementation of Green Pricing in the context of sustainable business.

Green Promotion represents a promotional strategy that focuses on environmentally friendly products. Based on data analysis, the X10 indicator shows the strongest influence with a factor loading of 0.87. This indicates that the promotion of green products has a very significant impact on the Green Promotion strategy. This high loading value emphasises the importance of companies to develop effective communication strategies in promoting their green products.

Indicators X12 with a factor loading of 0.82 and X11 with a factor loading of 0.78 also make a substantial contribution in forming the Green Promotion construct. These two indicators show an important role in supporting the success of green product promotion strategies, although not as strong as X10. The high loading values of the three indicators indicate that all aspects of green promotion complement each other in forming a comprehensive promotional strategy.

The existence of error terms (e10-e12) and Ze4 indicates that there are other variables outside the model that can affect the measurement results of Green Promotion. This reflects the complexity of green product promotion strategies that cannot be fully explained by only these three indicators. Nevertheless, the three existing indicators have provided a clear picture of the implementation of Green Promotion in the context of sustainable marketing.

Environmental Sustainability showed significant influence on various aspects of green marketing strategy. In the data analysis, Environmental Sustainability has a strong impact on four main elements: Green Product Design with a path coefficient of 0.45, Green Packaging with a coefficient of 0.56, Green Pricing with a value of 0.45, and Green Promotion with a coefficient of 0.49. Among the four elements, Green Packaging shows the strongest influence, indicating that the aspect of environmentally friendly packaging is the main focus in the implementation of environmental sustainability.

Environmental Sustainability also contributes to Reciprocal Value Product with a path coefficient of 0.35. Although the effect is not as strong as

the previous elements, it still shows that environmental sustainability plays a role in creating reciprocal value products.

The existence of error terms (Z_e) indicates that there are still other factors that can influence the relationship between Environmental Sustainability and these variables. This shows the complexity of the concept of environmental sustainability that cannot be fully explained only by the relationships in the model. Overall, however, Environmental Sustainability proved to be an important factor influencing various aspects of green marketing strategy and product value creation.

Green Competitive Position reflects the company's competitive position in the context of environmentally friendly strategies. Based on data analysis, indicator X20 shows the strongest influence with a factor loading of 0.70. This indicates that the green competitive position is a very important element in the company's competitive strategy. This high loading value emphasises the importance of building an environmentally-based competitive advantage.

Indicators X19 with a factor loading of 0.61 and X21 with a factor loading of 0.55 also make a significant contribution in forming the Green Competitive Position construct. Although the value is not as high as X20, these two indicators still show an important role in supporting the company's competitive position based on environmental sustainability.

The existence of error terms ($e_{19-e_{21}}$) and Z_{e6} indicates that there are other factors outside the model that can affect the measurement results of Green Competitive Position. This reflects the complexity of the green positioning strategy that cannot be fully explained by only these three indicators. Nevertheless, the three indicators have provided a good understanding of how companies can build and maintain their competitive position through a green approach.

Novelty Reciprocal Value Product shows an important role in creating innovative reciprocal value. Based on data analysis, this variable has a significant influence on Sustainable Competitive Advantage with a path coefficient of 0.26 and Green Consumerism with a higher coefficient of 0.38. The stronger influence on Green Consumerism indicates that product reciprocal

value has a greater impact on encouraging environmentally friendly consumption behaviour.

Reciprocal Value Product itself is influenced by Environmental Sustainability with a path coefficient of 0.35. This shows that environmental sustainability has an important role in shaping the reciprocal value of innovative products. This relationship confirms that environmental aspects are a key factor in developing product value that can provide reciprocal benefits.

The existence of error terms Ze_5 indicates that there are other factors outside the model that can affect Novelty Reciprocal Value Product. This reflects the complexity of creating reciprocal value that cannot be fully explained in the model. Nevertheless, the relationships identified demonstrate the strategic role of Novelty Reciprocal Value Product in linking environmental sustainability with competitive advantage and green consumer behaviour.

Green Consumerism reflects consumer behaviour that is oriented towards environmental sustainability. Based on data analysis, indicator X23 shows the strongest influence with a factor loading of 0.84. This indicates that green consumerism is a very important aspect in sustainable consumption patterns. This high loading value emphasises the importance of consumer awareness of environmentally friendly products.

Indicator X24 with a factor loading of 0.80 also makes a very significant contribution, almost on par with X23. Meanwhile, X22 with a factor loading of 0.73 also shows a fairly strong influence. The large loading values of these three indicators indicate that all aspects of Green Consumerism have an important role in shaping sustainable consumption behaviour.

The existence of error terms (e_{22} - e_{24}) and Ze_7 indicates that there are other factors outside the model that can affect the measurement results of Green Consumerism. This reflects the complexity of green consumer behaviour that cannot be fully explained by just these three indicators. Nevertheless, the three indicators have provided a comprehensive picture of how consumers adopt and apply the principles of environmentally friendly consumption in their purchasing decisions.

Green Brand Image represents brand perceptions associated with environmental commitment. Based on data analysis, indicator X26 shows the

strongest influence with a factor loading of 0.82. This indicates that green brand image has a very significant impact in shaping consumer perceptions of the brand. This high loading value emphasises the importance of building and maintaining an environmentally friendly brand image.

Indicator X25 with a factor loading of 0.81 shows almost equal influence with X26, indicating an equally important role in shaping Green Brand Image. Meanwhile, X27 with a factor loading of 0.73 also contributes significantly although not as high as the other two indicators. The large loading values of these three indicators indicate that all aspects play an important role in building an environmentally friendly brand image.

The existence of error terms (e25-e27) and Ze9 indicates that there are other factors outside the model that can affect the measurement results of Green Brand Image. This reflects the complexity of green brand image formation that cannot be fully explained by only these three indicators. Nevertheless, the three existing indicators have provided a comprehensive picture of how companies can build and maintain an environmentally friendly brand image.

Sustainable Competitive Advantage is a crucial factor in building a sustainable competitive advantage in an increasingly competitive global market. Based on the structural model analysis, indicator X29 emerged as the strongest contributor with a loading factor of 83, indicating the importance of building a sustainable competitive advantage. Porter & van der Linde, (2023) emphasise that sustainable competitive advantage is not only about operational efficiency, but also includes innovation and unique value creation for customers.

Indicators X28 and X30 with a loading factor of 82 and 72 respectively also contribute significantly in shaping sustainable competitive advantage. According to Hart, (2016) the integration of sustainability aspects into business strategy can create differentiation that is difficult for competitors to imitate. However, the presence of error terms e28-e30 and Ze8 indicates that there are still other factors that influence the formation of this sustainable competitive advantage.

Barney & Clark, (2023) added that achieving sustainable competitive advantage requires the development of organisational capabilities that are unique and difficult to imitate. This includes the ability to integrate environmental, social, and economic aspects in every strategic decision of the company, as well as building long-term relationships with stakeholders.

4.2 Discussion

Based on data found in the field, it states that consumers choose TikTok shop as a platform for online transactions due to several factors. The biggest factor is because the products in tiktokshop are more when they are online or live shop so the tendency to transact is very high when live.

The arguments given by respondents during the interview mentioned that consumers can interact with the seller and get an explanation of the product. education from the seller is needed by consumers so that they are not wrong when buying. In addition, consumers do not feel cheated after buying a product that does not match their expectations.

3.2 DISCUSSION

The failure of Indonesian agricultural and green products to enter the European market is a complex problem that has been going on for years. Based on data from the European Food Safety Authority (2023), the rejection rate of Indonesian products is still quite high, mainly due to non-compliance with the EU's strict food safety standards. Indonesian farmers and producers often find it difficult to fulfil HACCP requirements and EU organic standards, which are the main prerequisites for product entry into the European market.

To overcome these challenges, a comprehensive approach involving all stakeholders is needed. The government needs to strengthen support through training programmes, certification facilitation, and infrastructure development. The role of research institutions and universities is also important in developing technological innovations that can improve production efficiency and quality (Hersugondo *et al.*, 2025)

This problem is exacerbated by the structural conditions of Indonesian agriculture, which is still dominated by small farmers with fragmented land.

According to a World Bank report (2023), this fragmentation causes difficulties in quality standardisation and implementation of sustainable agricultural practices. Smallholders often do not have adequate access to modern technology, market information, and capital needed to improve the quality of their production.

Another significant challenge is the suboptimal supply chain system. Limited cold storage facilities and inadequate transport systems often lead to a decline in product quality during shipping. The Journal of Agriculture and Food Research (2023) notes that around 30 per cent of Indonesian agricultural products are damaged in the shipping process to Europe due to suboptimal cold chain management.

This research develops a new concept ‘Reciprocal of Value Product’ (RVP) adopted from Theory Reciprocal Mathematics (Lewis & Anderson, 2015), Mathematics for Business (Salzman & Clendenen, 2021), Maths Business Value (Limosin & Rigby, 2022) and synthesised with Theory of Relationship Marketing (Robert & Shelby, 1994), Service-Dominant Logic (Lusch & Vargo, 2006), Reciprocity in Marketing (Mustapha & Shamsudin, 2020).

This concept is defined as The reciprocal value of two or more business units that provide mutual benefits to the agreed product, this variable is thought to improve performance.

Figure 2
Synthesis of Reciprocal Concept of Value Product

The results of the theory synthesis from figure 2 can be explained as follows. The synthesis figure shows a conceptual diagram that explains the formation of 'Reciprocal of Value Product' as a new concept in the marketing domain. This diagram illustrates the train of thought and integration of various theories that resulted in the novelty in the field of marketing and value creation. At the top of the diagram, there are two fundamental theories at the root of this concept: 'Theory of Reciprocal Mathematics' on the left side and "Theory of Relationship Marketing" on the right side. These two theories form a solid theoretical basis for the development of the new concept. From the Theory of Reciprocal Mathematics, the path runs through 'Mathematics for Business' which then derives the concept of 'Multi Business Value'. This path illustrates how mathematical and quantitative aspects are integrated into the understanding of business value. This approach is the first novelty because it presents a quantitative, measurable perspective in assessing reciprocity in a business context (Vargo & Lusch, 2004).

On the right side of the diagram, the Theory of Relationship Marketing evolves into the 'Service-Dominant Logic' which then branches into two important concepts: 'Co-Creation' and "Relationship-oriented". This shows how the aspects of customer relationships and co-creation of value became key elements in the formation of the new concept. The second novelty lies in the systematic integration of the relationship marketing approach with mathematical principles (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004).

The synthesis figure shows a conceptual diagram that explains the formation of 'Reciprocal of Value Product' as a new concept in the marketing domain. This diagram illustrates the train of thought and integration of various theories that resulted in the novelty in the field of marketing and value creation. At the top of the diagram, there are two fundamental theories at the root of this concept: 'Theory of Reciprocal Mathematics' on the left side and "Theory of Relationship Marketing" on the right side. These two theories form a solid theoretical basis for the development of the new concept.

The centre of the diagram displays 'Reciprocity in Marketing' which is the meeting point of the various theoretical streams. This signifies the third novelty of placing reciprocity at the core of product value formation, shifting

the paradigm from exchange value to reciprocal value (Grönroos & Helle, 2012; Hidayah *et al.*, 2024)

At the bottom of the diagram, the ‘Reciprocal of Value Product’, signifying this as the final result or new concept generated. Its position at the bottom and connection to all elements indicates that this concept is a synthesis of all the components above it.

The novelty resulting from this integration includes several aspects:

- Development of a theoretical framework that integrates multiple streams of theory;
- Creation of a bridge between quantitative and qualitative approaches in marketing;
- Enrichment of the Service-Dominant Logic literature with a reciprocal perspective;
- Establishment of new metrics to measure product value;
- Practical guidance for the implementation of co-creation strategies.

This framework makes significant contributions both theoretically and practically. Theoretically, it enriches the understanding of value creation in marketing by integrating mathematical and relationship marketing perspectives. Practically, it provides a framework for developing more effective reciprocity-based marketing strategies (Lusch & Vargo, 2014).

Reciprocal of Value Product (RVP) is a fundamental concept in operations management that describes the reciprocal relationship between service providers and customers in the value creation process. This concept emphasises the importance of interaction and involvement of both parties to produce an optimal product or service.

The level of interaction and involvement required between the service provider/producer and the customer in the value creation and delivery process. The higher the RVP, the greater the customer involvement required (Chase & Garvin, 1989).

Appropriate mathematical calculations between business units so that they can benefit each other and build new research models by combining the RVP concept as a mediating variable with other variables such as the proposed hypothesis that the better the environmental sustainability supported by the

new concept of Reciprocal of Value and the variables of Green Competitive Position, Green Consumerims, and Green Brand Image, the stronger the position of Sustainable Competitive Advantage of Indonesian SMEs Food Products.

Table 2

Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Reciprocal_Value_Prod	<--	Environmental_sustaina	,700	,20	3,36	**	par_
cut	-	bility		8	8	*	2
Green_consumerism	<--	Reciprocal_Value_Prod	,417	,08	5,11	**	par_
	-	cut		2	6	*	3
Green_competitive_pos	<--	Reciprocal_Value_Prod	,466	,07	6,06	**	par_
ition	-	cut		7	9	*	4
Green_brand_image	<--	Green_consumerism	,338	,06	5,57	**	par_
	-			1	3	*	7

The following is a discussion of table 2. The results show that Environmental sustainability has a positive and significant influence on Reciprocal Value_Prodcut ($B = 0.700$, $p < 0.001$). This indicates that environmental sustainability contributes greatly to the reciprocal value of the product, these results are in line with research conducted (Dangelico & Vocalelli, 2017).

Reciprocal Value Prodcut has a significant positive impact on two constructs namely Green consumerism ($B = 0.417$, $p < 0.001$) and Green competitive position ($B = 0.466$, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that reciprocal value products influence green consumer behaviour and the company's green competitive position. These results are in line with research conducted (Chen *et al.*, 2006).

Reciprocal Value Product plays a strategic role in creating sustainable value for consumers and companies. Based on the structural model analysis, this variable shows a significant influence on Sustainable Competitive Advantage with a coefficient value of 26 and Green Consumerism with a coefficient of 38. According to Kotler & Armstrong, (2023) this reciprocal relationship reflects how sustainable products can create shared value between producers and consumers.

Environmental Sustainability exerts a substantial influence on Reciprocal Value Product with a coefficient of 35, emphasizing the importance of sustainability aspects in creating product value. Hoffman & Georg, (2024) highlighted that the integration of environmental values into product development not only improves competitiveness but also strengthens the brand's position in the eyes of environmentally conscious consumers. However, the presence of error terms Ze_5 indicates that there are other factors that influence the formation of this reciprocal value. Barathi *et al.*, (2025) added that the success of creating reciprocal value is highly dependent on the company's ability to integrate sustainability aspects into the entire value chain. This includes not only production aspects but also distribution, marketing, and sustainable after-sales services.

Green consumerism also has a positive and significant effect on Green brand image ($\beta = 0.338$, $p < 0.001$), implying that green consumerism contributes to the formation of green brand image, the results of this research are in line with the results of research conducted by the authors (Papadas *et al.*, 2017). The results of the data processing state that all construct relationships in the model are significant at the $p < 0.001$ level (marked with ***), this can be interpreted that there is a strong relationship between constructs. The C.R. (Critical Ratio) values for all relationships are above 1.96, reinforcing the statistical significance of these findings (Hair *et al.*, 2010).

The strong model fit indices (CFI = 0.932, TLI = 0.924, RMSEA = 0.052) indicate that the model effectively captures the complex interactions between these constructs. However, the high Chi-square value (540,839) relative to the degrees of freedom (315) indicates some potential for model refinement. a structural equation model and associated statistical output that examines the relationship between various green marketing concepts and sustainability. The model explores how sustainability initiatives and green marketing practices affect brand image, competitive position and overall business performance.

Thus, This model shows, Environmental Sustainability as a key variable that influences many aspects. Reciprocal Value Product as an important mediator High loading factors on the majority of indicators (>0.7) indicate good validity Goodness of fit indices (GFI, AGFI, CFI, TLI) >0.8 indicate good model

fit RMSEA 0.052 (<0.08) indicating the model has acceptable error. Overall, the model shows how environmental sustainability aspects influence various green business practices that ultimately contribute to sustainable competitive advantage. The indicators with the highest loading factor on each variable indicate the most critical aspects to be considered in the implementation of green business strategies.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The model provides important insights into how environmental sustainability and reciprocal product value influence consumer behaviour, competitive positioning, and brand image in the context of green marketing. The findings can assist companies in designing effective sustainability and marketing strategies.

The Main Relationship related to Environmental sustainability strongly influences 'Reciprocal Value Product' ($\beta = 0.700$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that sustainable practices significantly increase the perceived value of the product. Reciprocal Value products have a positive effect on green Consumerism ($\beta = 0.417$, $p < 0.001$) and green Competitive Positioning ($\beta = 0.466$, $p < 0.001$) as well as green Consumerism.

This relationship is in line with recent research on the effectiveness of green marketing. For example, a meta-analysis Wang *et al.*, (2023). found that green marketing strategies positively influence consumer purchase intentions and brand perceptions, especially when supported by genuine sustainability practices. This model incorporates several key elements of a green marketing strategy including Green product design, Green packaging, Green pricing, Green promotion. This holistic approach reflects the concept of the 'green marketing mix', which is an extension of the traditional 4Ps of marketing. As noted by (Rahman & Nguyen-Viet, 2023), successful green marketing requires the integration of sustainability across all aspects of the marketing mix to create a coherent and credible green value proposition.

The model also highlights the role of 'green consumerism' as a mediating factor between sustainable product attributes and brand outcomes. This is in

line with the findings from (Mehraj & Qureshi, 2022), that consumer environmental awareness significantly moderates the effectiveness of green marketing efforts. The model also links this green marketing construct to competitive outcomes, Green competitive positioning with sustainable competitive advantage.

This relationship underscores the strategic importance of sustainability initiatives in modern business. As argued (Rubio-Andrés *et al.*, 2022) recent work on Creating Shared Value, sustainability can be a source of innovation and competitive differentiation if fully integrated into business strategy.

The role of technology and innovation has also become very important in optimising green product design. Seuring & Müller, (2024) highlight the importance of investment in research and development to create design solutions that are not only environmentally friendly but also economical and acceptable to the market. This reflects the complexity of achieving a balance between aspects of sustainability, functionality and economic viability in green product development.

This concept proves that the success of increasing the success of Indonesian products in the European market will depend on the ability of all stakeholders to collaborate in overcoming various challenges. Long-term commitment and continuous investment are required, especially in the aspects of quality improvement, technology adoption, and human resource development. With the large potential of the European market and the increasing trend of sustainable product consumption, systematic efforts to improve the competitiveness of Indonesian products in the European market must continue so that sustainable development goals (SDGs) for economic growth can be achieved.

5 IMPLICATION MANAGERIAL

Despite the challenges, the promising potential of the European market makes improving the quality and standardisation of Indonesian agricultural products an important priority. With systematic improvements in various aspects, from production to delivery, it is expected that Indonesian agricultural

products and environmentally friendly products can penetrate the competitive and profitable European market, so that sustainable development goals (SDGs) for economic growth can be achieved.

Companies can leverage the concept of Reciprocal Value Products to improve their environmental sustainability, enhance their competitive position, and foster stronger relationships with environmentally conscious consumers. Managers should focus on creating products that offer reciprocal benefits to consumers and the environment by Designing products with longer lifetimes to reduce waste and Using recyclable or biodegradable materials by developing Reciprocal Value Products that have a significant impact on products.

The strong influence of environmental sustainability on Reciprocal Value Products prioritises sustainable practices in their product development and operations. This may include Implementing environmentally friendly production processes Sourcing sustainable raw materials and Reducing the carbon footprint throughout the supply chain.

Capacity building of farmers and SMEs, strengthening infrastructure, and appropriate policy support will be the key to successful penetration of the European market. Learning from the success of neighbouring countries such as Thailand and Vietnam can also be a valuable reference in developing more effective strategies. This model provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the relationship between environmental sustainability, green marketing mix, and competitive advantage in a modern business context.

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